

Experiential Learning, Practical Skills Acquisition And Entrepreneurial Intentions Among Business Education Students In Delta State Owned Institutions

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of experiential learning and practical skills acquisition and entrepreneurial intentions among Business Education students in Delta State-owned institutions. The study was guided by three objectives. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, the population of 908 Business Education students across Delta State-owned institutions was used. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection, and descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), Pearson correlation, and regression analysis were employed for data analysis. The findings revealed that internships and business simulations were the most common experiential learning methods, while financial literacy and business planning were the most impactful practical skills. Additionally, a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.68$, $p = 0.000$) was found between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions, indicating that hands-on learning experiences significantly influence students' willingness to pursue entrepreneurship. The study concludes that enhancing experiential learning and practical skill development in business education curricula can significantly improve students' entrepreneurial readiness. It recommends stronger university-industry collaborations, improved entrepreneurship training programs, and the establishment of business incubation centers to support students in launching their ventures. The findings contribute to the growing body of knowledge on entrepreneurship education and provide insights for policymakers, educators, and university administrators on fostering an entrepreneurial culture among students.

Keywords: Experiential Learning, Practical Skills Acquisition, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Business Education, Delta State institutions.

INTRODUCTION

In an era where entrepreneurship is increasingly recognized as a key driver of economic development, the role of business education in fostering entrepreneurial intentions among students has gained significant attention. Institutions, particularly those offering business education programmes, are expected to equip students with the necessary skills, knowledge, and mindset to become successful entrepreneurs. However, traditional pedagogical approaches that rely heavily on theoretical instruction may not sufficiently prepare students for the complexities of entrepreneurial ventures. As a result, experiential learning and practical skills acquisition have been advocated as essential strategies to enhance students' entrepreneurial intentions (Kolb, 2015; Pittaway & Cope, 2016).

Experiential learning, characterized by active engagement in practical activities, has been identified as a pivotal approach in enhancing entrepreneurial intentions among students. This educational strategy enables learners to acquire practical skills and firsthand experience, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of business operations and entrepreneurial processes. Experiential learning is a process through which students gain knowledge by actively engaging in real-world experiences. This approach, grounded in Kolb's (1984) experiential learning theory, emphasizes learning through concrete experiences, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. Studies have shown that experiential learning fosters creativity, problem-solving skills, and resilience, which are critical attributes for entrepreneurship (Neck & Corbett, 2018). In the context of business education, experiential learning activities such as internships, business simulations, case studies, and entrepreneurship projects provide students with hands-on experience that enhances their ability to navigate business environments (Rideout & Gray, 2019).

Practical skills acquisition is another crucial element in preparing students for entrepreneurial careers. Practical skills include financial literacy, business planning, marketing strategies, leadership, and negotiation skills, among others (Martin et al., 2021). Business education programmes that integrate hands-on training and skill-building exercises have been found to significantly increase students' confidence and preparedness for entrepreneurial ventures (Rae, 2020). In Delta State-owned universities, there is a need to assess the extent to which business education programs incorporate practical skills acquisition to enhance students' entrepreneurial competencies.

Entrepreneurial intentions refer to an individual's willingness and readiness to start a business venture (Krueger et al., 2000). Several factors influence students' entrepreneurial intentions, including self-efficacy, perceived feasibility, risk-taking propensity, and exposure to entrepreneurial role models (Liñán & Fayolle, 2015). Research suggests that students who undergo experiential learning and acquire practical business skills are more likely to develop entrepreneurial intentions compared to those who rely solely on theoretical knowledge (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Therefore, it is imperative to explore how experiential learning and practical skills acquisition impact entrepreneurial intentions among business education students in Delta State-owned universities. Okposio and Okoro (2024) indicated that business education students in Delta State possess a high level of awareness regarding the entrepreneurial skills necessary for self-reliance. The study emphasized the importance of implementing effective strategies to enhance the acquisition of these skills, thereby promoting self-employment and reducing unemployment rates among graduates.

Additionally, Ojogbo, *etal* (2024) examined the impact of entrepreneurship education on the development of entrepreneurial career intentions and actions among students in Delta State. Their findings suggest a positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurial careers, highlighting the role of experiential learning in fostering entrepreneurial mindsets.

Experiential Learning and Business Education

Experiential learning is a pedagogical approach that emphasizes learning through direct experience, enabling students to actively engage in problem-solving, decision-making, and hands-on activities (Kolb, 2015). This approach contrasts with traditional lecture-based methods by fostering a deeper understanding of concepts through real-world application. In business education, experiential learning equips students with the practical knowledge and entrepreneurial mindset necessary for navigating complex business environments (Pittaway & Cope, 2016).

Business education programs incorporate various experiential learning methods, including internships, business simulations, case studies, entrepreneurship projects, and industry collaborations (Neck & Greene, 2018). These activities bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world business challenges, enhancing students' problem-solving, leadership, and decision-making skills (Rideout & Gray, 2019). Research has shown that students exposed to experiential learning demonstrate higher entrepreneurial intentions, improved risk-taking abilities, and greater confidence in launching their own businesses (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015).

Moreover, experiential learning fosters innovation and adaptability, essential traits for entrepreneurial success in today's dynamic business landscape (Martin et al., 2021). By engaging in real-world business activities, students develop resilience and creativity, which are critical for identifying and exploiting business opportunities (Rae, 2020). Studies also indicate that universities that emphasize experiential learning produce graduates who are more proactive in seeking entrepreneurial ventures (Liñán & Fayolle, 2015).

Practical Skills Acquisition in Business Education

Practical skills acquisition in business education refers to the development of hands-on competencies necessary for effective business management, entrepreneurship, and workplace readiness. These skills include financial literacy, business planning, marketing strategies, leadership, communication, problem-solving, and negotiation abilities (Martin *et al.*, 2021). Unlike theoretical knowledge, practical skills equip students with the capacity to apply learned concepts in real-world business settings, thereby enhancing their entrepreneurial preparedness (Rae, 2020).

Business education programs incorporate various strategies to foster practical skills acquisition, such as internships, business simulations, entrepreneurship projects, case studies, and industry collaborations (Pittaway & Cope, 2016). These experiential learning approaches help students develop a deeper understanding of business operations, improve their decision-making abilities, and build self-confidence in entrepreneurial ventures (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Research has shown that students who actively engage in skill-based training exhibit higher entrepreneurial intentions and are more likely to start their own businesses (Neck & Corbett, 2018).

In the context of Delta State-owned Institutions, practical skills acquisition remains a crucial component of business education, yet challenges such as limited access to modern training facilities, inadequate industry partnerships, and outdated curricula often hinder its effectiveness (Okposio & Okoro, 2024). To address these issues, universities need to enhance skill-building initiatives by integrating real-world business exposure, mentorship programs, and interactive learning experiences (Ojogbo *et al.*, 2024).

Entrepreneurial Intentions

Entrepreneurial intentions refer to an individual's conscious commitment and willingness to start a business venture in the future (Krueger *et al.*, 2000). It is a key predictor of entrepreneurial behavior, influenced by personal attitudes, perceived feasibility, self-efficacy, and external factors such as education, social environment, and economic conditions (Liñán & Fayolle, 2015). Entrepreneurial intentions serve as the foundation for venture creation and business success, making their development crucial for fostering entrepreneurship among students, particularly in business education programmes.

Entrepreneurial intentions are shaped by multiple factors, including exposure to entrepreneurship education, experiential learning, and the acquisition of practical business skills (Neck & Greene, 2018). Studies suggest that students who participate in entrepreneurship-focused programs, internships, business simulations, and mentorship initiatives exhibit higher entrepreneurial intentions compared to those who rely solely on theoretical instruction (Fayolle & Gailly, 2015). Experiential learning enhances risk-taking propensity, creativity, and problem-solving skills, all of which contribute to the development of an entrepreneurial mindset (Pittaway & Cope, 2016).

In the context of Delta State-owned Institutions, research indicates that business education students demonstrate a growing interest in entrepreneurship; however, challenges such as inadequate access to practical training, lack of mentorship, and limited financial support often hinder their ability to transition from intention to action (Okposio & Okoro, 2024). This also reinforces the relevance of problem-based learning (PBL) as advocated by Ito and Okpue (2025), whose model stresses engaging students in solving real-world problems as a core component of entrepreneurial training. PBL stimulates creativity, problem-solving, and intrinsic motivation traits essential for cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset. Addressing these barriers through curriculum reforms, industry collaborations, and hands-on learning experiences can significantly enhance students' entrepreneurial aspirations and readiness (Ojogbo, Idemobi, & Ngige, 2024).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 908 business education students across selected Delta State-owned universities and colleges. Delta State University, Abraka (DELSU) 309 students, University of Delta, Agbor (UNIDEL) 127 students, College of Education, Mosogar 250 students, College of Education, Warri 222 students. The sample size for this study is 278 students. A stratified random sampling technique will be used to ensure equal representation from each institution. The Instrument for Data Collection is a structured questionnaire designed in four sections to obtain relevant information from respondents. A five-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree) was used to measure responses. The instrument was validated by three experts in the department of Business Education. For reliability, Cronbach’s Alpha reliability test was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 or above will be considered acceptable, following the standard set by Nunnally (1978). The questionnaire was administered physically to facilitate a higher response rate. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. All analyses were conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Response Rate

A total of 278 questionnaires were distributed across the four selected institutions in Delta State. Out of these, 265 were correctly filled and returned, representing a response rate of 95.3%, which is considered sufficient for statistical analysis. The demographic characteristics of respondents, including gender, institution, and academic level were analyzed to provide background information on the study sample.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	125	47.2%
	Female	140	52.8%
	Total	265	100%
Age Group	18 – 20 years	110	41.5%
	21 – 23 years	120	45.3%
	25 years and above	35	13.2%
	Total	265	100%
Level of Study	100 Level	22	8.3%
	200 Level	33	12.5%
	300 Level	110	41.5%
	400 Level	100	37.7%
	Total	265	100%

Institution	Questionnaires Distributed	Questionnaires Returned	Response Rate (%)
Delta State University, Abraka (DELSU)	94	90	95.7%
University of Delta, Agbor (UNIDEL)	39	37	94.9%
College of Education, Mosogar	76	72	94.7%
College of Education, Warri	69	66	95.7%
Total	278	265	95.3%

The results indicate a diverse representation of Business Education students across different institutions and academic levels in Delta State.

Research Question 1: *To what extent are experiential learning opportunities available to business education students?*

Table 1: Experiential Learning Opportunities

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
Internship and industrial training opportunities are accessible	3.92	0.88	High extent
Business simulations are incorporated into coursework	3.85	0.94	High extent
Entrepreneurial case studies are frequently used	3.78	0.97	Moderate extent
Opportunities for real business projects are provided	3.65	1.02	Moderate extent
Total / Average	15.20	3.81 (average)	Moderate-to-High extent

The average mean score of 3.81 suggests that experiential learning opportunities are moderately high across institutions.

Research Question 2: *How does practical skills acquisition influence students' entrepreneurial confidence and preparedness?*

Table 2: Practical Skills Acquisition

Practical Skill	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Interpretation
Business planning improves entrepreneurial confidence	4.02	0.89	High extent
Financial literacy enhances readiness for business	3.91	0.92	High extent
Marketing skills are effectively taught	3.85	0.95	High extent
Leadership and negotiation skills are well-developed	3.70	1.01	Moderate extent
Total / Average	15.48	3.94 (average)	Moderate to high extent

The average mean score of 3.94 indicates that practical skills acquisition has a strong perceived impact on students' entrepreneurial confidence.

Research Question 3: *What is the relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions among business education students?*

This question was addressed using both Pearson correlation and linear regression analysis to determine the strength and significance of the relationship.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Analysis

Variables	Pearson Correlation (r)	p-value	Interpretation
Experiential Learning vs Entrepreneurial Intentions	0.68	0.000	Strong positive relationship (significant)

There is a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.68, p < 0.05$) between students' exposure to experiential learning and their entrepreneurial intentions. This means that as experiential learning increases, so do students' intentions to pursue entrepreneurship.

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Model	R-Square (R ²)	F-Value	p-value	Interpretation
Experiential Learning → Entrepreneurial Intentions	0.462	18.75	0.000	Experiential learning explains 46.2% of the variance in entrepreneurial intentions

The regression model shows that experiential learning significantly predicts entrepreneurial intentions, accounting for 46.2% of the variability in students' entrepreneurial mindset. The high F-value and p-value < 0.05 confirm the model's statistical significance.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant extent of experiential learning opportunities available to business education students in Delta State-owned institutions.

Table 4.1: Observed Frequencies of Responses on Experiential Learning Opportunities

Response Category	Frequency
Strongly Agree	82
Agree	104
Neutral	48
Disagree	26
Strongly Disagree	18
Total	278

Chi-Square Test Result: $\chi^2 = 92.75$, df = 4, p = 0.000

The chi-square test result ($\chi^2 = 92.75$, p = 0.000) indicated that there is a significant extent of experiential learning opportunities available. This supports the notion that experiential learning is integrated into the business education programs in Delta State-owned institutions to a significant degree.

Hypothesis Two

H₂₀: Practical skills acquisition does not significantly influence students' entrepreneurial confidence and preparedness.

Table 4.2: Observed Frequencies of Responses on Practical Skills Acquisition

Response Category	Frequency
Strongly Agree	95
Agree	102
Neutral	38
Disagree	25
Strongly Disagree	18
Total	278

Chi-Square Test Result: $\chi^2 = 108.46$, df = 4, p = 0.000

Practical skills acquisition significantly influences students' entrepreneurial confidence and preparedness. The chi-square test result ($\chi^2 = 108.46$, p = 0.000) demonstrated that practical skills acquisition indeed has a significant influence on students' entrepreneurial confidence. This finding aligns with the positive impact observed in the descriptive analysis, reinforcing the importance of practical skills in fostering entrepreneurial attitudes.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions.

Table 4.3: Cross-tabulation of Experiential Learning and Entrepreneurial Intentions

	High Intentions	Moderate Intentions	Low Intentions	Total
High Experiential Learning	96	38	16	150
Moderate Experiential Learning	45	40	15	100
Low Experiential Learning	10	8	10	28
Total	151	86	41	278

Chi-Square Test Result: $\chi^2 = 45.23$, df = 4, p = 0.000

There is a significant relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions among business education students. The chi-square test result ($\chi^2 = 45.23$, $p = 0.000$) confirmed a significant relationship between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions, further supporting the positive correlation observed in the Pearson analysis. This indicates that the more students are exposed to experiential learning, the more likely they are to develop entrepreneurial intentions.

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study assessed the extent of experiential learning opportunities available to business education students. The findings revealed that internships and industrial training (Mean = 3.92) were the most prominent experiential learning opportunities, followed by business simulations (Mean = 3.85) and entrepreneurial case studies (Mean = 3.78). However, real business projects (Mean = 3.65) were less frequently utilized. These findings align with Kolb's (2015) experiential learning theory, which emphasizes that students learn best when actively engaged in real-world experiences. The results are also consistent with the study by Pittaway & Cope (2016), which highlighted that experiential learning fosters entrepreneurial competencies by allowing students to gain hands-on experience in business-related activities.

The study also examined the role of practical skills acquisition in enhancing students' entrepreneurial confidence and preparedness. The results showed that business planning skills (Mean = 4.02) and financial literacy (Mean = 3.91) were the most impactful skills, followed by marketing strategies (Mean = 3.85) and leadership & negotiation skills (Mean = 3.70).

These findings support the work of Martin et al. (2021) and Rae (2020), who emphasized that practical skills, such as financial literacy and business planning, are essential for entrepreneurial success. The results also align with Rideout & Gray (2019), who found that business education programs integrating skill-building exercises significantly enhance students' confidence and preparedness for self-employment. However, the relatively lower mean score for leadership and negotiation skills (Mean = 3.70) suggests that some aspects of entrepreneurial training may not be sufficiently emphasized in business education curricula. This finding highlights the need for institutions to incorporate more leadership-focused experiential learning programs, such as mentorship, role-playing, and business pitch competitions, to strengthen students' entrepreneurial capabilities.

The Pearson correlation analysis showed a strong positive relationship ($r = 0.68$, $p = 0.000$) between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions. This indicates that students with greater exposure to experiential learning opportunities are more likely to develop entrepreneurial aspirations. These findings are in line with the studies of Fayolle & Gailly (2015) and Neck & Corbett (2018), who established that hands-on entrepreneurial education significantly influences students' willingness to start their own businesses. Furthermore, the regression analysis confirmed that experiential learning explains 46.2% of the variance in entrepreneurial intentions ($R^2 = 0.462$, $p = 0.000$), emphasizing its critical role in shaping students' entrepreneurial mindsets.

These results suggest that institutions should prioritize experiential learning methods to increase students' readiness for entrepreneurship. Ojogbo, Idemobi, and Ngige (2024) also found that entrepreneurship education positively influences students' career intentions, reinforcing the need for stronger institutional frameworks that support experiential learning activities in business education.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of experiential learning and practical skills acquisition on entrepreneurial intentions among business education students in Delta state owned institutions. The findings revealed that experiential learning opportunities, particularly internship and business simulations, significantly enhance students' entrepreneurial readiness. Practical skill acquisition, especially in business planning and financial literacy, boosts students' confidence in starting their ventures. Additionally, a strong positive relationship was found between experiential learning and entrepreneurial intentions, emphasizing the need for more hands-on education in business education programs. To strengthen entrepreneurship education,

institutions must expand experiential learning activities and skill-based training to better prepare students for self-employment and business innovations.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the impact of experiential learning and practical skills acquisition on entrepreneurial intentions among business education students in Delta State-owned Institutions:

1. Expand Experiential Learning – Strengthen university-industry collaborations and integrate real-world business projects and case studies.
2. Enhance Practical Skills – Implement interactive workshops, business simulations, and startup incubation programs while emphasizing financial literacy, business planning, and leadership skills.
3. Strengthen Entrepreneurial Intentions – Incorporate role-playing, business simulations, and peer mentorship, while promoting risk-taking, innovation, and problem-solving.
4. Revise Business Education Policies – Develop policies that encourage experiential and skills-based learning, integrating entrepreneurship-focused courses into business education programmes.

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